

PATTERN OF SERUM ELECTROLYTES (SODIUM & POTASSIUM) IN PATIENT WITH HEPATIC ENCEPHALOPATHY ADMITTED IN A TERTIARY LEVEL HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hepatic encephalopathy is an important complication of liver disease causing significant morbidity and mortality. Analysis of the course and variation in the biochemical parameters during the disease process is needful for better understanding and management of disease. Aim of the study was to find out the electrolyte status of a hepatic encephalopathy patient. **Methods:** This hospital based cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Department of Medicine in Dhaka Medical College Hospital, for a period from July 2019 to December 2019. All patients of hepatic encephalopathy were approached for participation of the study and included in this study according to selection criteria. Following informed written consent, detailed history, physical examination and necessary investigations were performed. Data had been collected by interview using a structured questionnaire. Collected data had been analyzed by the SPSS 21. **Results:** Total 50 subjects were studied with prime clinical

features were altered consciousness (100%), Jaundice (100%), ascites (80%), splenomegaly (78%), flapping tremor (62%). Most common precipitating factors were Upper GI bleeding (64%), infections (36%) and constipation (12%). Of all, 38% of study population had grade III Hepatic encephalopathy, 30% had grade IV, 18% had grade II and 14% grade I. They had significant Hyponatremia with a mean serum Na⁺ level of 130.97±4.57 mmol/L & serum K⁺ of 4.24±0.79 mmol/L. **Conclusion:** In this study both sodium and potassium level altered in Hepatic Encephalopathy patients. However, further study with larger sample size is recommended.

KEYWORDS: *Hepatic encephalopathy, Hyponatremia, Hypokalaemia, Jaundice.*

INTRODUCTION

Hepatic encephalopathy is an important complication of liver disease causing significant morbidity and mortality worldwide. Hepatic encephalopathy in cirrhosis can result in persistent cognitive dysfunction that can affect daily functioning and health-related quality of life.^[1] It is a reversible syndrome of impaired brain function occurring in patients with advanced liver failure. However, hepatic encephalopathy is not a single clinical entity. It may reflect either a reversible metabolic encephalopathy, brain atrophy, brain oedema or any combination of these conditions. The mechanisms causing brain dysfunction in liver failure are still unknown. These factors are directly related to liver failure (e.g. decreased metabolism of ammonia). Unless the underlying liver disease is successfully treated, hepatic encephalopathy is associated with poor survival and a high risk of recurrence.^[2] It includes the spectrum of potentially reversible neuropsychiatric abnormalities such as personality changes, intellectual impairment and a depressed level of consciousness are seen in patients with liver dysfunction after exclusion of unrelated neurological and or metabolic abnormalities. Most manifestation of hepatic encephalopathy are reversible with prompt medical treatment.^[3] Hepatic encephalopathy may be clinically apparent in as many as one third of cirrhotic patients and, if rigorously tested, up to two thirds have some degree of mild or subclinical hepatic encephalopathy. An important prerequisite for the syndrome is diversion of portal blood into the systemic circulation through portosystemic collateral vessels.^[4] Pathogenesis of hepatic encephalopathy is complex where hyperammonaemia plays key role. The liver normally metabolizes gut toxins, so, during hepatocellular failure and portal-systemic shunting, toxins reach the systemic circulation, and eventually the brain. In adaptive response, astrocytes convert ammonia into glutamine, changing cellular

osmolality, drawing in water, causing astrocyte swelling and potentiating cerebral oedema.^[5] There is little information on factors predictive of the development of hepatic encephalopathy. Earlier studies in patients treated with surgical portosystemic shunts as well as recent studies in patients treated with trans jugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunts (TIPS) represents a major risk factor for the development of hepatic encephalopathy in patients with cirrhosis. Finally, there are other conditions not directly related to Porto-systemic shunting or liver failure that are frequently present in patients with cirrhosis and may theoretically represent a risk factor for the development of hepatic encephalopathy. A particularly interesting condition is hyponatraemia, which is associated with marked changes in the central nervous system because of the reduction in plasma osmolality.^[6] The diagnosis of hepatic encephalopathy is based on a clinical examination and a clinical decision. Clinical scales are used to analyse its severity. Specific ‘quantitative’ tests are only needed in study settings. The ‘gold standard’ is the West-Haven criteria (WHC). In patients with evidently altered consciousness, the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) is widely employed.^[7] In patients with liver failure, electrolyte and acid–base status gets disrupted with the disease progression, infection, dietary indiscretion/deprivation, or pharmacological intervention. Hyponatremia, hypokalaemia, and metabolic alkalosis are well-recognized triggers of hepatic encephalopathy (HE). The development of portal hypertension, a result of endothelial dysfunction fostered by liver fibrosis, leads to upregulation of the endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) pathway and increased nitric oxide (NO) levels. Endothelial mechanoenzyme pathways involving integrin linked kinases have been postulated to regulate eNOS expression and function. Increases in NO promote splanchnic vasodilation, clinically manifested by a decrease in blood pressure (BP), which is perceived as a decrease in effective arterial volume by the kidney and large vessel baroreceptors. In turn, this activates the renin–angiotensin–aldosterone system (RAAS) and the non-osmotic release of arginine vasopressin (AVP) with subsequent sodium and water retention (leading to ascites and hyponatremia). Furthermore, elevations of NO in plasma parallel the development of renal dysfunction in decompensated patients. As the disease progresses, the increase in total body water plus the increased portal resistance and intense splanchnic vasodilation lead to an increase in vascular hydrostatic pressure. Concurrently, the reduced synthetic capacity of the liver leads to hypoalbuminemia and a resulting decrease in intravascular oncotic pressure. When considering these forces, the net driving force for filtration through the intestinal capillary leads to ascites formation. Therefore, ascites is perpetuated in a vicious cycle of sensed “underfilling” despite clinical “overfilling”, resulting in a constant release of AVP (in

addition to its decreased clearance). High blood ammonia levels alone do not add any diagnostic, staging or prognostic value in hepatic encephalopathy patients with chronic liver disease.^[8] Analysis of the course and variation in the biochemical parameters during the disease process might help in the better understanding and management of the disease process.^[9] Electrolyte disorders such as hyponatremia parallel liver disease progression and become a short-term indicator of a poor prognosis. Hyponatremia, hypokalaemia, and metabolic alkalosis are well-recognized triggers of hepatic encephalopathy.^[10] Hepatic encephalopathy has been shown in several studies to be worsened by the presence of hyponatraemia. Hyponatraemia with serum sodium 130 mEq/L is one of several predictive factors, along with a history of encephalopathy, serum creatinine and bilirubin, for the development of overt hepatic encephalopathy.^[11] Hyponatremia is frequently observed in patients with cirrhosis. A pathophysiology of hyponatremia is based on systemic hemodynamic abnormalities caused by impaired renal water retention. Since the systemic circulation may be affected by portal hypertension due to the increased intrahepatic resistance, the hyperdynamic state and the development of collateral vessels, this suggests a close link between portal hemodynamic and hyponatremia.^[12] Serum sodium is primarily regulated by aldosterone, which also regulates serum potassium. Hence, whether potassium homeostasis also has any prognostic significance in these patients, it remains questionable as there are no studies that have investigated this issue.^[13] In patients with cirrhosis the prognosis of the episode of hepatic encephalopathy is usually dictated by the underlying precipitating factor. Patients with cirrhosis that have experienced an episode of hepatic encephalopathy should be considered candidates for liver transplant. The recurrence of hepatic encephalopathy is more common in patients that develop progressive deterioration of liver function and hyponatremia.^[14] Recovery from hepatic encephalopathy is especially likely to occur if a major precipitating factor can be clearly identified and removed or corrected.^[15] In Bangladesh, many patients are admitted in different hospitals with liver cirrhosis related to hepatic encephalopathy as a cause of complication. But there is little study regarding electrolyte imbalance and prognosis of hepatic encephalopathy. The importance of this study is to have a better understanding the relation between serum electrolytes & hepatic encephalopathy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted in the at the in-patient department of medicine at Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Dhaka. During the period from July 2019 to December 2019. Pattern of

Serum Electrolytes (Sodium & Potassium) in Patient with Hepatic Encephalopathy Admitted in a Tertiary Level Hospital. Total 50 patients were selected according to inclusion and exclusion criteria. Informed written consent was taken from each patient/first hand guardian. All clinical information, socio demographic information was taken, and relevant investigations were done. All data had been recorded in separate pre-designed case record forms. All data had been checked and analysed using software SPSS-21. Descriptive statistics were used: Mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for continuous variables. Absolute numbers and percentages for categorical variables. Student's t-test was used for significance testing, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant

RESULT

Sociodemographic Characteristics

Among 50 patients with hepatic encephalopathy (HE), majority were from 51-60 years group (28.0%) followed by 20% in 41-50 years group. Mean age was 50.94 ± 14.22 years with age ranging from 23-78 years. Male: Female is 2.33:1. Seventy percent study population were from rural area followed by 30% from urban in the study. Ninety-two percent study population were the believers of Islam and rest 8% were Hindu. Among 50 patients with hepatic encephalopathy, 72% were married and 12% unmarried. Majority study subjects were from lower class family followed by 32% middle class and rest 20% from upper class.

Table I: Sociodemographic Characteristics: (n=50)

Age (in years)	Number of patients (n)	Percentage (%)
≤ 30	5	10
31-40	8	16
41-50	20	20
51-60	14	28
61-70	8	16
>70	5	10
Mean \pm SD (yrs)	50.94 ± 14.22	
Male: Female	2.33:1	
Religion	Number of patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Islam	46	92
Hindu	4	8
Marital Status	Number of patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Married	36	72
Unmarried	6	12
Residence	Number of patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Urban	15	30
Rural	35	70
Socioeconomic Condition	Number of patients (n)	Percentage (%)

Lower Class	24	48
Middle Class	16	32
Upper Class	10	20

Clinical features of hepatic encephalopathy patients

All the patients had altered consciousness (100%) and jaundice (100%) followed by 80% ascites, 78% splenomegaly, 62% had flapping tremor. Other major clinical features are tabulated below.

Table II: Clinical features of hepatic encephalopathy patients in the study (n=50).

Clinical features	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Altered Consciousness	50	100
Jaundice	50	100
Ascites	40	80
Splenomegaly	39	78
Flapping Tremor	31	62
Anaemia	22	44
Edema	19	38
Vomiting	16	32
Fever	11	22
*Multiple responses considered		

Precipitating factors for hepatic encephalopathy: Upper GI bleeding was found to be the most common precipitating factors for hepatic encephalopathy patients (64%), followed by infections (36%) and constipation (12%). Other causes are given in following table.

Table III: Precipitating factors for hepatic encephalopathy in study population (n=50).

Precipitating factors	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Upper GI Bleeding	32	64
Infection	18	36
Constipation	7	14
Excessive protein rich food intake	6	12
Excessive use of diuretics	5	10
Dehydration	3	6
Use of sedative	2	4
Alcohol Consumption	1	2
*Multiple responses considered		

Grades of hepatic encephalopathy: Majority study population had grade III hepatic encephalopathy (38%) while 30% had grade IV.

Figure I: Distribution according to grades of hepatic encephalopathy (HE) (n=50).

Serum sodium level in hospital admitted hepatic encephalopathy

Hyponatremia was recorded in 72.0% patients among whom 24% had mild and 48% had significant hyponatremia. Mean serum Na^+ level was recorded 130.97 ± 4.57 mmol/L.

Table IV: Serum sodium level in hospital admitted hepatic encephalopathy patient of our study (n=50).

Serum Na^+	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Hyponatremia (<135 mmol/L)		
Mild (134-130 mmol/L)	12	24
Significant (<130 mmol/L)	24	48
Normal (135-145 mmol/L)	14	28
Total	50	100
Mean Serum Na^+ (mmol/L)	130.97 ± 4.57	

Serum potassium level in hospital admitted hepatic encephalopathy patient: Among 50 hepatic encephalopathy patients, 74% had normal serum K^+ level followed by 20% had hypokalemia and 6% had Hyperkalemia. Mean serum K^+ was recorded 4.24 ± 0.79 mmol/L.

Table V: Serum potassium level in hospital admitted hepatic encephalopathy patient of our study (n=50).

Serum K^+	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Hypokalemia (<3.5 mmol/L)	10	20
Normal (3.5-5.0 mmol/L)	37	74
Hyperkalaemia (>5 mmol/L)	3	6
Total	50	100
Mean Serum K^+ (mmol/L)	4.24 ± 0.79	

Relation of serum sodium level with grades of hepatic encephalopathy: Following table is showing the severity of hepatic encephalopathy depending on the serum sodium concentration differed significantly among the groups ($p < 0.001$).

Table VI: Relation of serum sodium level with grades of hepatic encephalopathy (n=50).

Sodium level	Grades of hepatic encephalopathy				P-value
	Grade I	Grade II	Grade III	Grade IV	
Mild Hyponatremia (134-130 mmol/L)	0	3 (33.3%)	8 (42.1%)	1 (6.7%)	<0.001*
Significant Hyponatremia (<130 mmol/L)	0	0	11 (57.9%)	13 (86.7%)	
Normal Sodium level (135-145 mmol/L)	7 (100%)	6 (66.7%)	0	1 (6.7%)	
Total	7 (100%)	9 (100%)	19 (100%)	15 (100%)	

*p-value determined by chi-square (χ^2) test

Relation of serum potassium level with grades of hepatic encephalopathy: Hypokalemia was observed in 85.7% cases of grade I hepatic encephalopathy patients and 33.3% patients with grade II hepatic encephalopathy patients. Otherwise, majority study subjects with different grades of HE had normal potassium value which shows statistically significance ($p < 0.001$).

Table VII: Relation of serum potassium level with grades of hepatic encephalopathy (n=50).

Potassium level	Grade of encephalopathy				P-value
	Grade I	Grade II	Grade III	Grade IV	
Hypokalemia (<3.5 mmol/L)	6 (85.7%)	3 (33.3%)	1 (5.3%)	0	<0.001*
Normal Potassium (3.5-5.0 mmol/L)	0	6 (66.70%)	16 (84.20%)	15 (100%)	
Hyperkalemia (>5 mmol/L)	1 (14.3%)	0	2 (10.50%)	0	
Total	7 (100%)	9 (100%)	19 (100%)	15 (100%)	

*P-value determined by chi-square (χ^2) test

DISCUSSION

We evaluated the associations of serum electrolyte levels especially serum sodium and potassium obtained in hospital admitted hepatic encephalopathy patients. In this study 50 patients with hepatic encephalopathy were studied in a tertiary care hospital and all factors which are important in causing hepatic encephalopathy were investigated and analyzed. In the

present study, out of 50 patients, the age incidence was more in 51-60 years of age (28.0%), followed by 41 to 50 years (20%). The minimum age was 23 years, and the maximum was 78 years with a mean age of 50.94 ± 14.22 years. Which is comparable to the study by Onye were CA *et al.* where the mean age was 47 years, Bagny *et al.* where it was also 48.9 ± 13 years and Dixit *et al.* where it was 54 ± 11.1 years 41–43.^[16,17] Majority patients were Muslims (92%) and were married (72%) in our study. Majority of patients in this study were from rural areas (70%) and belong to poor socioeconomic group (48%). The negative aspect for the rural population is that they reached the tertiary care hospital in the late phase. Amongst the clinical findings, jaundice in 100%, altered conscious state (ranging from confusion to coma) in 100%, ascites in 80% and splenomegaly in 78% were the most common presenting features in this study. Flapping tremor was seen in 62%, anemia in 44%, pedal edema in 38%. In previous studies by Kabir *et al.* also recorded that jaundice and altered consciousness were the commonest features of hepatic encephalopathy.^[18] Gastrointestinal bleeding (64%), infection (36%) and constipation (14%) were common precipitating factors detected in our study. Increased ammonia production by the gut urease forming bacteria and/or reduced hepatic perfusion would explain the occurrence of HE in gut bleeders. Prophylactic use of B-blockers and nitrates for non-bleeders, along with implementation of the available endoscopic facilities for variceal eradication, are strongly advised for variceal bleeders. In eastern series, infections come in second place as an important HE precipitant of hepatic encephalopathy.^[19] While in the West, infections were blamed in 3%-4% of cases only.^[20] The high frequency of infections in this study probably reflects the hygienic, nutritional, and immune status of the studied 46 cases. Thus, magnifying the role of the caring physicians, especially in primary health care centers, in filling these observed patient's health status gaps. Kumar *et al.* (39%) also found it as the most common cause where Maqsood *et al.* recorded as the 2nd most common cause.^[21,22] In this study 38% of individuals presented with grade III encephalopathy with respect to 30% grade IV and 18% grade II and 14% grade I. Similar observations were noted by Benhar *et al.* in their study where 36% of patients suffered from grade IV encephalopathy and 31% from grade III.^[23] Similar results were observed by Raphael *et al.* where 36.4% individuals presented with grade III encephalopathy.^[24] Among 50 patients, 72% had hyponatremia among whom 24% had mild (130-135 mmol/L) and rest 48% had significant (<130 mmol/L) hyponatremia. Mean serum sodium level was 130.97 ± 4.57 mmol/L. In a Korean study, prevalence of hyponatremia at a serum sodium <135 mmol/L was 47.9% in hospitalized patients, and that of severe hyponatremia at a serum sodium <130 mmol/L was 27.1%.^[25] The severity of hepatic encephalopathy in our study increased with

the decreasing level of serum sodium concentration which is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) which is consistent with the findings of Kim *et al.* in Korea.^[25] In previous study by Gurunamasivayam *et al.* it was observed that, patients with higher grades of hepatic encephalopathy had lower serum sodium level which is like our findings.^[9] The relationship between hepatic encephalopathy and serum levels may be explained based on more severe liver failure among patients with serum sodium < 130 mmol/L and the possibility that the two events may be pathophysiologic ally linked. Low serum sodium levels in patients with cirrhosis are associated with a remarkable reduction in the cerebral concentration of organic osmolytes that probably reflect compensatory osmoregulatory mechanisms against cell swelling.^[26-28] Hypokalaemia was observed in 20% patients with HE in our study followed by 6% had hyperkalaemia and rest 74% had normal serum potassium level. Mean serum K⁺ level was 4.24 ± 0.79 mmol/L. In previous study, hypokalaemia was found in 11% Abu-Assi *et al.*, 18% Alam *et al.* and 18% Fallon *et al.* who had shown variable frequency of hypokalaemia in subjects suffering from chronic liver disease with complications or with treatment.^[18,19,29] Extracellular hydrogen moves into the cells to maintain Electroneutrality, thus ammonia production increases due to intra cellular acidosis in renal tubular cell. The conversion of ammonium (NH₄⁺) is promoted by concomitant contribution of metabolic alkalosis; NH₄⁺ is a charged element that cannot cross the blood brain barrier, while ammonia can enter the brain. Among grade I hepatic encephalopathy, hypokalaemia was observed in 85.7% cases while 33.3% patients with grade II hepatic encephalopathy had hypokalaemia in the study. In a cross-sectional study by Jamali *et al.* It was observed that, 72% subjects of chronic liver disease were found hypokalaemia, among them 25% had the symptoms of hepatic encephalopathy that validates the strong association of hypokalaemia with hepatic encephalopathy.^[30,23]

CONCLUSION

This study showed that initial serum sodium and potassium measurements were in altered level making dyselectrolytemia as a common manifestation accompanied with hepatic encephalopathy.

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